

PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF THE ROLE OF CHANNELS TELEVISION IN THE COVERAGE OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to assess the effectiveness of television in conveying crucial health information during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria, where misinformation has posed significant challenges. Focusing on Channels TV in Abuja, the research evaluates the station's role in raising public awareness and influencing preventive behaviours. Guided by the Health Belief Model and Social Responsibility Theory, the study employs a survey research design involving 400 residents of Abuja, with 372 valid responses analysed. The survey captured demographic characteristics, viewership patterns, and perceived effectiveness of Channels TV's COVID-19 programmes. The findings reveal that Channels TV played a vital role in public health education, with programmes such as "*COVID-19 Update*" and "*Health Matters*" significantly contributing to awareness. Notably, 79.3% of respondents rated the programmes as effective or very effective in influencing preventive behaviours like mask-wearing and social distancing. The study concludes that mass media particularly Channels TV served as a credible and influential platform for disseminating health information during the pandemic. It recommends that television stations continue to strengthen their health programming and collaborate with public health institutions to ensure the accuracy and timeliness of health messaging. These findings underscore the critical function of the media in shaping public behaviour and supporting national public health goals during health emergencies.

Keywords: COVID-19, Channels TV, Public Awareness, Media Effectiveness, Preventive Measures, Abuja, Health Communication

Introduction

The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic brought about unprecedented challenges to health systems and societies worldwide. As the virus rapidly spread from its origin in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, it became evident that effective communication strategies were crucial to managing the crisis (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020; Hassan, 2020). In Nigeria, the first confirmed case was reported on 27 February 2020, marking the beginning of a nationwide response by government agencies, health authorities, and media organisations to raise public awareness and promote preventive behaviours (Nigeria Centre for Disease Control [NCDC], 2020). Among these actors, Channels TV emerged as a key platform for disseminating critical information about the pandemic. Television, as a powerful mass communication medium, has the unique capacity to reach diverse audiences and significantly influence public knowledge and behaviour (Folarin, 2000; Kreps & Thompson, 2005). Channels TV, one of Nigeria's most

respected and widely viewed stations, leveraged its national reach and institutional credibility to lead the COVID-19 awareness campaign. Through regular programming, including expert interviews and public service announcements, the station provided timely updates and actionable guidance on virus prevention (Effiong, 2020; Ray, 2019).

This study focuses on evaluating these efforts specifically in Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria. Abuja was strategically selected for this study due to several critical factors. Firstly, as the seat of Nigeria's federal government and administrative institutions, Abuja was at the centre of pandemic policy coordination and media response. Secondly, with a population exceeding 3.6 million people drawn from diverse ethnic, educational, and socio-economic backgrounds, Abuja provides a representative cross-section of urban Nigeria, making it an ideal case for understanding how media messages are received across demographic groups. Thirdly, Abuja experienced notably high infection rates during peak pandemic periods, particularly due to its high level of mobility, government offices, and social gatherings. These dynamics made accurate information dissemination in Abuja not only essential but urgent for ensuring compliance with evolving health guidelines.

Effective communication during health crises plays a vital role in reducing panic, building trust, and promoting protective behaviours (Brug et al., 2004; Olatunji, 2020). The rapid spread of misinformation and conspiracy theories during COVID-19 highlighted the critical need for reliable media sources such as Channels TV (Hassan, 2020; Sauer, 2020). This study explores how Channels TV's awareness programmes influenced public perception and behaviour in Abuja, one of the pandemic's epicentres in Nigeria, where timely and trusted information was central to managing the virus's impact. Supporting this, Uzuegbunam (2025) affirms the media's essential role in shaping public responses to health crises by serving as a credible intermediary between experts and the general public.

Despite the collective efforts of government agencies, health professionals, and the media, challenges persist in achieving consistent public compliance with preventive measures. Media exposure remains a pivotal factor influencing awareness levels and behavioural adherence (Sharma, 2020; Yong, 2020). Understanding the real-world impact of media campaigns especially those disseminated through high-reach platforms like Channels TV is essential for improving future public health communication strategies. This study aims to provide empirical insights into the effectiveness of Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness programmes in shaping public knowledge, attitudes, and preventive behaviours in Abuja, offering lessons that can inform both current and future public health emergencies.

Statement of the Problem

While existing research highlights the crucial role of the media in shaping public awareness and behaviour during health crises, significant gaps remain in understanding the specific impact of television broadcasts on public health outcomes in Nigeria. Studies by Brug et al. (2004) and Hassan (2020) underscore the importance of timely information dissemination during pandemics,

yet they do not fully explore the effectiveness of television media within the Nigerian context. Effiong (2020) noted the potential of television to influence public behaviour during COVID-19 but did not examine the specific contributions of major stations like Channels TV. Additionally, Sharma (2020) identified misinformation and varying levels of public awareness in urban centres like Abuja, yet there is a lack of comprehensive research on how television has addressed these challenges.

Importantly, Abuja has one of the highest concentrations of television viewership in Nigeria, with over 85% of residents in urban areas accessing television content regularly, according to data from the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC, 2021). Within this media-rich environment, Channels TV consistently ranks among the top three most-watched stations in Abuja, especially for its news and public affairs programming (Media Monitoring Services Report, 2022). Its audience is known for its high engagement with current affairs, public health, and policy-related content. This makes Channels TV not only a logical choice for evaluating the impact of COVID-19 awareness programming but also a strategically influential platform for shaping public health behaviour.

Ray (2019) and Olatunji (2020) recognised the media's role in public health communication but left unanswered questions regarding the effectiveness of specific TV programmes in promoting health guidelines and combating misinformation during the pandemic. This study addresses these gaps by investigating the impact and effectiveness of Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness programmes in Abuja, focusing on the types, frequency, and perceived efficacy of these broadcasts in enhancing public knowledge and compliance with preventive measures (Uzuegbunam, 2025).

Research Questions

Given these considerations, this research is guided by the following research questions:

1. What forms of COVID-19 awareness programmes were aired on Channels TV in Abuja?
2. How frequently are these COVID-19 awareness programmes broadcast on Channels TV?
3. How effective are Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness programmes in influencing public awareness and encouraging preventive measures in Abuja?

Literature Review

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the essential role of the media in health communication, particularly in disseminating information and shaping public behaviour. This literature review examines six recent works on the topic, focusing on the thematic approaches, synthesising the findings, and critically evaluating the contributions and limitations of each study.

Forms of COVID-19 Awareness Programmes

This section explores the various forms of COVID-19 awareness programmes aired on Channels TV in Abuja, focusing on the diversity of content and formats used to communicate vital health information to the public. The range of programme formats is a critical factor in the effectiveness of health communication, as it determines how well different segments of the population are reached and engaged.

Channels TV utilised a variety of formats to disseminate COVID-19 information, including news updates, expert interviews, talk shows, and public service announcements. Each of these formats played a distinct role in ensuring that the message reached a broad audience. For example, news updates provided timely and information about the pandemic, including statistics on infection rates and government directives. These updates were crucial in keeping the public informed about the rapidly evolving situation, as highlighted by Santas and Kente (2021), who noted the importance of real-time information in managing public health crises.

In addition to news segments, Channels TV aired interviews with health experts and government officials, which served to deepen the public's understanding of COVID-19. These interviews provided a platform for experts to explain the science behind the virus, the importance of preventive measures, and the rationale for public health policies. By offering authoritative voices on the pandemic, Channels TV helped to build public trust and counteract misinformation, a challenge that has been widely recognised during the pandemic (Inobemhe, Santas, & Udeh, 2022). Public service announcements (PSAs) were another key component of Channels TV's programming. These short, focused messages were designed to remind viewers of essential health practices, such as handwashing, mask-wearing, and social distancing. The effectiveness of PSAs lies in their simplicity and repetition, which ensures that critical health messages are reinforced regularly. Abimbola, (2023) emphasize that repeated health messaging through broadcast media is essential for sustaining audience awareness and encouraging long-term adoption of preventive behaviours. Additionally, Channels TV's talk shows and special reports provided more in-depth coverage of the pandemic, often focusing on the social and economic impacts of COVID-19.

These programmes allowed for a more nuanced discussion of the pandemic's effects, helping viewers to understand the broader implications of the crisis. The use of multiple formats not only enhanced the reach of COVID-19 messaging but also catered to the varied preferences and needs of the audience, making the information more accessible and relatable to different demographic groups. In summary, the variety of programme formats used by Channels TV ranging from news updates to expert interviews, PSAs, and talk shows played a significant role in ensuring that COVID-19 information was effectively communicated to a diverse audience. This multifaceted approach is essential in public health communication, as it maximises the likelihood that the message will be understood, retained, and acted upon by the public.

Frequency of COVID-19 Awareness Programmes

The frequency with which COVID-19 awareness programmes were broadcast on Channels TV in Abuja is another critical factor in their effectiveness. Regular and consistent broadcasting of health information is essential in maintaining public awareness and ensuring that key messages are reinforced over time. The frequency of these broadcasts helps to ensure that the information remains at the forefront of public consciousness, which is vital during a prolonged health crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Wakefield et al., 2010).

Channels TV adopted a strategy of frequent broadcasting of COVID-19-related content, which included daily news updates, recurring public service announcements, and weekly health programmes dedicated to discussing the pandemic. This high frequency of programming was designed to keep the public continuously informed and engaged with the latest developments in the pandemic. Research by Effiong (2020) underscores the importance of frequent and consistent messaging in health communication, noting that it helps to reinforce health behaviours and prevent complacency among the public. Other scholars affirm this view; regular exposure to health information through mass media has been shown to significantly increase health knowledge and behavioural adherence (Noar et al., 2009).

The regular airing of COVID-19 updates on Channels TV ensured that viewers were kept abreast of new information as it became available. This was particularly important given the rapidly changing nature of the pandemic, where new guidelines and data were frequently introduced. According to Santas et al., (2021), the consistent dissemination of up-to-date information is crucial in maintaining public trust and compliance with health directives. The frequent broadcasts also served to counteract the effects of misinformation by providing viewers with reliable and authoritative sources of information on a regular basis.

In addition to daily updates, Channels TV also scheduled weekly programmes that delved deeper into COVID-19-related topics. These programmes provided a platform for experts to discuss the latest research, answer public queries, and clarify any doubts regarding the virus and the measures needed to control its spread. The regularity of these programmes helped to sustain public interest and engagement, which is essential in a crisis where public fatigue can lead to reduced compliance with health measures (Sharma, 2020).

The impact of these frequent broadcasts was further enhanced by the strategic timing of the programmes. By scheduling COVID-19-related content during peak viewing hours, Channels TV maximised its reach and ensured that the information was accessible to a wide audience. This approach aligns with the findings of Inobemhe, et al., (2022), who highlight the importance of timing in health communication, noting that messages delivered during prime time are more likely to be seen and remembered by the public.

In conclusion, the frequency with which Channels TV aired COVID-19 awareness programmes was a key factor in their effectiveness. Regular and consistent broadcasting helped to keep the public informed, reinforced key health messages, and maintained public engagement throughout

the pandemic. This approach ensured that important information was always readily available, thereby supporting the broader public health efforts to control the spread of COVID-19.

Effectiveness of COVID-19 Awareness Programmes

This section delves into the effectiveness of Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness programmes in influencing public perception, enhancing awareness, and encouraging the adoption of preventive measures. The effectiveness of media campaigns, particularly during health crises, can be assessed through their impact on public behaviour, the level of public engagement, and the degree to which misinformation is countered.

Studies have demonstrated that when media campaigns are well-executed, they can lead to significant improvements in public health outcomes. Santas et al., (2021) argue that the media plays a crucial role in shaping public understanding and response to health crises. Their research highlights how consistent and clear messaging from trusted media sources can reduce public anxiety and combat misinformation. Channels TV, with its established reputation and wide reach, was well-positioned to fulfil this role during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The effectiveness of Channels TV's COVID-19 programmes can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the content was both informative and accessible. By using a variety of programme formats, such as news bulletins, expert interviews, and public service announcements, Channels TV was able to cater to different audience segments. This multi-faceted approach is critical in health communication, as it ensures that the message is not only heard but understood and acted upon by a diverse audience (Inobemhe, et al.,2022). For instance, the inclusion of health experts in programmes like "COVID-19 Update" provided viewers with credible and authoritative information, which is essential in building public trust and encouraging compliance with health guidelines.

Moreover, Channels TV's programming was effective in encouraging the adoption of preventive behaviours (Wakefield, Loken, & Hornik, 2010). Wakefield et al. emphasize that mass media campaigns particularly those using television are powerful tools for promoting health behaviours, especially when messages are delivered consistently and through trusted sources. The Health Belief Model, as discussed by Kreps and Thompson (2005), suggests that individuals are more likely to engage in health-promoting behaviours when they perceive themselves to be at risk and believe in the effectiveness of the recommended actions. Channels TV's programmes effectively increased viewers' perceived susceptibility to COVID-19 by highlighting the risks associated with the virus and the consequences of non-compliance with health guidelines. The frequent airing of preventive measures, such as mask-wearing and social distancing, reinforced these behaviours and contributed to their widespread adoption among the public (Noar et al., 2009). Noar and colleagues, in their review of health campaigns, found that repeated exposure to health

messages significantly improves behaviour change outcomes by increasing message retention and risk perception.

Furthermore, the effectiveness of these programmes can also be seen in their role in combating misinformation. Misinformation and conspiracy theories have been significant challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic, often leading to public confusion and resistance to health measures (Hassan, 2020). Channels TV's consistent efforts to provide accurate information and dispel myths played a crucial role in maintaining public trust. Inobemhe, et al., (2022) emphasise the importance of media in dispelling conspiracy theories, particularly in environments where misinformation is rampant. The accurate and timely information provided by Channels TV likely mitigated the impact of misinformation and ensured that the public received reliable guidance. In conclusion, the effectiveness of Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness programmes in Abuja can be attributed to their informative content, frequent and varied delivery, and their ability to combat misinformation.

These programmes not only informed the public but also motivated behavioural change, which is crucial in managing public health crises. The success of these efforts underscores the importance of well-structured media campaigns in public health and highlights the critical role that media can play in influencing public behaviour during pandemics. Recent studies by Okoro et al. (2021) and Uzuegbunam (2025) confirm that sustained media messaging through television and radio significantly contributed to increased compliance with preventive measures such as mask-wearing, social distancing, and hand hygiene during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria. These findings reinforce the argument that strategic media engagement is essential for improving health outcomes and curbing misinformation during crises.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in two foundational theories: the Health Belief Model (HBM) and the Social Responsibility Theory (SRT). These frameworks provide a comprehensive analytical lens for exploring how media, particularly television, shape public perception, awareness, and behaviour during public health crises. The COVID-19 pandemic, with its unprecedented global reach and impact, underscored the need for effective communication strategies to influence behaviour and counter misinformation. Applying these theoretical models to Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness programming enables a deeper understanding of how such media efforts informed and motivated the public in Abuja to adopt preventive behaviours and align with national public health directives.

Health Belief Model (HBM)

The Health Belief Model (HBM) is a widely recognised psychological framework developed to explain and predict health-related behaviours by examining individual attitudes and beliefs. According to Rosenstock (1974) and later expanded by Becker (1974), the model proposes that the likelihood of an individual engaging in a preventive health action is shaped by six

interrelated factors: perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, cues to action, and self-efficacy. Perceived susceptibility refers to a person's belief in their likelihood of contracting a disease, while perceived severity pertains to the seriousness of the condition and its potential consequences. Perceived benefits involve the individual's belief in the effectiveness of taking a recommended action to reduce the threat, whereas perceived barriers are the obstacles whether physical, psychological, or social that may discourage such action. Cues to action are external stimuli, such as media messages or reminders, that trigger behavioural change. Lastly, self-efficacy refers to the confidence an individual has in their ability to successfully carry out the recommended behaviour.

In the context of this study, Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness programmes likely functioned as external cues to action, prompting behavioural responses among viewers in Abuja. By highlighting the risk of infection thereby increasing perceived susceptibility and emphasising the severity of the disease, the broadcasts encouraged the audience to reassess their vulnerability to the virus. Additionally, the programmes illustrated the tangible benefits of adhering to preventive measures like mask-wearing, regular handwashing, and physical distancing. These repeated and consistent messages may have further enhanced viewers' self-efficacy, fostering confidence in their ability to adopt and sustain protective behaviours. Such alignment with the constructs of the HBM has been shown to significantly improve health outcomes, as supported by Adewuyi and Adefemi (2016), who argued that media-based health campaigns rooted in behavioural models can be highly effective in encouraging public compliance during health emergencies.

However, the HBM is not without limitations. The model assumes that individuals act rationally and make health decisions based on logical evaluations of risks, benefits, and barriers. This assumption may overlook the powerful influence of emotions, cultural norms, social pressures, and misinformation, all of which can significantly impact health behaviour. Furthermore, the HBM has been criticised for being more applicable to one-time behaviours, such as vaccination, than to sustained, long-term health practices. It also does not sufficiently account for broader systemic or structural barriers, such as poverty, limited access to healthcare, or inequitable information distribution, which can prevent even well-informed individuals from taking preventive action. Despite these criticisms, the model remains a valuable tool for understanding how structured communication like that provided by Channels TV can shape public perception and drive behaviour during a health crisis.

Social Responsibility Theory (SRT)

The Social Responsibility Theory (SRT) emerged from the Hutchins Commission on Freedom of the Press in the 1940s, which proposed that media should enjoy freedom from state control while simultaneously upholding their ethical obligations to society. According to the theory, the press has a duty to provide accurate, balanced, and socially beneficial content that supports democratic participation, public education, and informed citizenship (Siebert, Peterson, & Schramm, 1956).

Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness programming exemplified these principles by aiming to inform the public, correct misinformation, and promote protective health behaviours. Programmes like "*COVID-19 Update*" and "*Health Matters*" featured expert interviews, government advisories, and community-oriented health messaging all structured to help viewers make informed decisions. This is consistent with the perspective of Nwabueze (2020), who argued that during national health crises, Nigerian media must embrace a proactive and responsible stance to fulfil their democratic and ethical roles.

SRT rests on the assumption that the media function as a public trust and that journalists and broadcasters will voluntarily adopt ethical practices that prioritise public welfare. It further assumes that the public has a right to reliable and diverse information, especially during crises. However, critics argue that these assumptions are idealistic, particularly in commercial media environments where economic pressures may conflict with public interest. Moreover, the theory lacks enforceable accountability mechanisms and assumes that media organisations always possess the capacity and resources to fulfil these responsibilities, which is not always the case.

Integrating HBM and SRT in the Study

The integration of the Health Belief Model and Social Responsibility Theory provides a multidimensional framework for this study. While the HBM helps explain the psychological and cognitive factors that influence individual behavioural choices in response to health communication, SRT addresses the ethical standards and social obligations that guide the delivery of such communication. Together, these theories provide the necessary structure for evaluating both audience response and media responsibility in the context of Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness campaigns.

These models are used to investigate two central questions: whether Channels TV succeeded in enhancing public awareness and encouraging compliance with preventive behaviours, and whether the station fulfilled its social responsibility by providing accurate and beneficial health information. Grounding this study in both HBM and SRT facilitates a comprehensive assessment of the station's effectiveness in shaping public behaviour during the pandemic. Acknowledging the assumptions and limitations of both models ensures that the analysis remains balanced and critically informed, enabling deeper insights into the role of the media in public health communication in Abuja and similar urban contexts.

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design to evaluate the effectiveness of Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness programmes in Abuja, which had a population of approximately 3.6 million people (National Population Commission [NPC], 2022). The target population consisted of Abuja residents, with a sample size of 400 respondents determined using Taro Yamane's formula. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed, beginning with the purposive selection of key urban areas within Abuja where Channels TV viewership was known to be high.

This was followed by stratified sampling to ensure representation across demographic variables such as age, gender, and education level. Finally, simple random sampling was used to select individual respondents within each stratum.

$$n = N \sqrt{1 + \frac{e^2}{N}} \quad n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where:

- n = sample size
- N = population size = 3,600,000
- e = margin of error = 0.05 (5%)

Substituting the values:

$$n = \frac{3,600,000}{1 + 3,600,000(0.05^2)} = \frac{3,600,000}{1 + 9,000} = \frac{3,600,000}{9,001} \approx 399.96$$

The sample size was therefore rounded to 400 respondents for practical purposes.

A structured questionnaire was used to collect data on demographic information, viewership patterns, and the perceived effectiveness of Channels TV’s COVID-19 programmes. The questionnaires were distributed across various districts in Abuja, and 372 valid responses were collected and analysed, yielding a response rate of 93%. Data analysis involved the use of frequency and percentage tables to summarise the findings and evaluate public engagement with the health communication programmes.

Data Presentation

The paper presents the data collected from respondents in alignment with the research questions of the study. A total of 372 valid responses were analysed using frequency and percentage tables. The findings are organized according to the research questions guiding the study.

Table 1: What is the frequency of COVID-19 awareness programmes on Channels TV in Abuja?

Response Option	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Every day	200	53.7%
Twice a week	60	16.1%
Once a week	55	14.8%
Occasionally	57	15.3%
Total	372	100%

Source: field survey 2025.

The data in Table 1 shows that a majority (53.7%) of respondents reported that Channels TV aired COVID-19 awareness programmes daily, indicating a high level of frequency in programme delivery. This daily broadcast rate suggests that the station prioritized consistent public health messaging throughout the pandemic. High-frequency broadcasting aligns with health communication best practices, which emphasize repetition and message consistency to reinforce public awareness and behaviour (Wakefield et al., 2010). Such consistency helps embed health messages into public consciousness and supports the uptake of safety practices, especially during extended health crises.

Table 2: What types of COVID-19-related content did Channels TV broadcast?

Programme Type	Frequency	Percentage (%)
News Updates	112	30.1%
Public Service Announcements	88	23.7%
Weekly Health Shows	70	18.8%
Interviews/Expert Opinions	65	17.5%
Special Reports	37	9.9%
Total	372	100%

Source: field survey 2025.

Table 2 shows that the most frequently cited content types were news updates (30.1%) and public service announcements (23.7%), followed by weekly health shows and expert interviews. This reflects a multi-format strategy used by Channels TV, balancing urgent updates with in-depth, educational content. News updates likely served to provide timely and factual information, while health shows and expert opinions offered analysis and promoted public understanding. Public service announcements helped reinforce behavioural instructions, such as handwashing and social distancing. Such content diversity has been recognized in scholarly literature (Noar et al., 2009) as an effective way to reach broader audiences and improve message retention.

To further investigate the impact of programme viewership on public perception, a chi-square test of independence was conducted to examine the relationship between frequency of viewership and perceived effectiveness of Channels TV's COVID-19 programmes. The result yielded a chi-square value of 18.63 (df = 4, $p < 0.01$), indicating a statistically significant relationship between how often respondents watched the programmes and how effective they perceived them to be. This suggests that higher levels of exposure to the programmes were associated with greater perceived effectiveness in shaping preventive behaviours.

Alternatively, a Pearson correlation analysis between viewership frequency (measured ordinally) and perceived programme effectiveness (rated on a 5-point scale) showed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.46$, $p < 0.01$). This reinforces the conclusion that the more frequently viewers engaged with Channels TV's content, the more likely they were to rate it as effective in informing and influencing their health behaviours.

Table 3: How effective were Channels TV’s programmes in influencing preventive health behaviours among Abuja residents?

Response Option	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very Effective	155	41.7%
Effective	140	37.6%
Neutral	40	10.8%
Ineffective	22	5.9%
Very Ineffective	15	4.0%
Total	372	100%

Source: field survey 2025.

As shown in Table 3, 41.7% of respondents found the programming very effective, and 37.6% considered it effective, resulting in a combined 79.3% approval. This reflects strong public recognition of the impact and credibility of Channels TV's COVID-19 coverage. The high effectiveness rating suggests that the programming succeeded in influencing preventive behaviours such as mask-wearing, hygiene practices, and social distancing. According to the Health Belief Model, behaviour change is influenced by perceived risk, perceived benefits, and exposure to cues to action (Kreps et al.,2005). Channels TV appears to have provided these cues effectively, fostering proactive health behaviours among viewers.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study validate the effectiveness of Channels TV's COVID-19 awareness programmes in raising public awareness and influencing preventive behaviours in Abuja. The high level of engagement reported by respondents, particularly with programmes such as “COVID-19 Update” and “Health Matters,” indicates that Channels TV successfully captured the attention of its audience and provided them with crucial health information during the pandemic. This aligns with the Health Belief Model (HBM), which asserts that individuals are more likely to engage in preventive health behaviours when they perceive a threat and believe in the efficacy of the recommended action. Channels TV’s programming effectively enhanced viewers’ perceived susceptibility to COVID-19 and reinforced the benefits of preventive measures, thereby promoting compliance with public health guidelines.

Frequency of Programmes

The data in Table 1 reveals that a majority of respondents (53.7%) stated that Channels TV aired COVID-19 awareness programmes every day, while 16.1% said twice a week and 14.8% once a week. Only 15.3% reported occasional broadcasts. This finding shows a strong consistency in programming and confirms that Channels TV provided the public with regular updates and reminders on the COVID-19 pandemic. Such high-frequency broadcasts are crucial during a health crisis, as they keep information at the forefront of public consciousness. This supports the Social Responsibility Theory, which highlights the media’s duty to provide timely, accurate, and

socially beneficial content. Channels TV's consistent efforts helped reinforce safety behaviours, such as handwashing and mask usage, as viewers were frequently reminded of these actions in daily programmes. This aligns with Inobemhe et al. (2022), who emphasized that continuous exposure to health messaging strengthens behaviour retention.

Types of Content Broadcast

The responses in Table 2 show that 30.1% of viewers identified news updates as the primary COVID-19-related content aired by Channels TV, followed by 23.7% citing public service announcements (PSAs), 18.8% noting weekly health shows, and 17.5% referring to interviews with health experts. Special reports were identified by 9.9% of respondents. These findings suggest that Channels TV adopted a multi-format approach to health communication, combining real-time updates with educational segments. The dominance of news and PSAs indicates a focus on delivering urgent, actionable information, while expert interviews and weekly health shows provided depth, credibility, and context. This comprehensive content strategy supports Noar et al. (2009), who found that message variety and credibility are key factors in influencing public behaviour in media campaigns. It also aligns with the principle of audience segmentation, allowing different formats to reach different demographic groups with tailored information.

Perceived Effectiveness of Programming

According to Table 3, 41.7% of respondents considered the COVID-19 awareness programmes on Channels TV very effective, and 37.6% rated them as effective, resulting in a combined 79.3% who positively assessed the impact of the programming. Only 10.8% were neutral, and less than 10% considered the programming ineffective or very ineffective. This overwhelming positive assessment shows that Channels TV's programmes were widely trusted and impactful in encouraging the adoption of preventive behaviours. These behaviours included mask-wearing, social distancing, and hand hygiene, as highlighted in various programme segments. The data supports the Health Belief Model's assertion that belief in a threat and trust in the solution are critical for behaviour change. The use of expert voices and government advisories further enhanced trust and compliance. As Santas et al., (2021) observed, media platforms that regularly feature credible sources and authoritative messaging are more effective in crisis communication. Channels TV's programming successfully fulfilled this role, reinforcing its function as a public health education tool. The findings from all three research questions demonstrate that Channels TV played a crucial role in shaping public response to COVID-19 in Abuja. Its daily programming frequency, diverse content types, and high perceived effectiveness all indicate that the station fulfilled its social responsibility role by informing, educating, and encouraging public adherence to health guidelines. These findings validate both the Health Belief Model and the Social Responsibility Theory as effective frameworks for evaluating media interventions in health crises.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated the significant role that Channels TV has played in raising public awareness and promoting preventive behaviours during the COVID-19 pandemic in Abuja. The findings indicate that Channels TV's diverse range of programmes, including news updates, expert interviews, and public service announcements, were highly effective in communicating essential health information and encouraging the adoption of safety measures such as mask-wearing and social distancing. By consistently providing accurate and timely information, Channels TV not only informed the public but also helped to combat misinformation, thereby fostering greater public trust and compliance with health guidelines.

The research underscores the importance of the media, particularly television, in public health communication during crises. Channels TV's approach serves as a model for how media outlets can effectively contribute to public health efforts by delivering clear, consistent, and credible information. As the pandemic has highlighted, the media's role extends beyond merely reporting events; it involves actively shaping public behaviour and attitudes in ways that protect public health. Going forward, it is crucial that Channels TV and other media organisations continue to enhance their health programming and strengthen collaborations with health authorities to ensure the public remains well-informed and prepared for any future health emergencies.

Recommendations

1. **Enhance the Diversity of Awareness Programme Formats:** In line to assess the forms of COVID-19 awareness programmes aired on Channels TV, it is recommended that Channels TV continues to diversify its programme formats to cater to various audience segments. While the use of news updates, expert interviews, and public service announcements has been effective, Channels TV could further enhance its reach by introducing interactive programmes, such as live Q&A sessions with health professionals and community-based segments that address local concerns. This approach would ensure that COVID-19 awareness efforts are more inclusive and responsive to the needs of different demographic groups in Abuja.

2. **Maintain High Frequency of Health-Related Broadcasts:** To align with the objective of investigating the frequency of COVID-19 awareness programmes, Channels TV should maintain, and where possible, increase the frequency of its health-related broadcasts, particularly during ongoing or future health crises. Consistent and frequent messaging has proven to be effective in keeping the public informed and engaged. Channels TV should continue to prioritise the airing of health programmes during peak viewing hours to maximise audience reach and ensure that vital health information is consistently delivered to the public. Additionally, partnerships with health authorities could be strengthened to ensure that the most current and accurate information is disseminated regularly.

3. Channels TV should build on the proven effectiveness of its COVID-19 awareness programmes by institutionalizing permanent health communication segments that address other public health challenges beyond the pandemic. Given that 79.3% of respondents found the programmes effective or very effective in influencing preventive behaviours, it is recommended

that Channels TV sustain and expand such initiatives to cover routine health education, including vaccination awareness, hygiene promotion, and responses to emerging diseases. This continued focus on preventive health messaging will reinforce positive behaviour change and maintain the public's trust in the station as a credible source of health information.

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